

**THE ROLE OF PUPPET THEATRES IN EDUCATING THE YOUNG GENERATION IN
THE SPIRIT OF LOVE FOR THE MOTHERLAND****Azamjon Abdukhalilov**

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Abstract

This article discusses puppet theatre, which is considered a unique form of theatrical art, and its dramaturgy. It also reflects on the significance of puppet theatre performances in the upbringing of the younger generation.

Keywords: theatre, puppet theatre, theatrical art, audience, moral education, children's psychology.

Today's youth are the owners of tomorrow's country. This concept and such an assessment of society have become the main essence of state policy in our country. Our rapidly changing life is increasingly filled with various contradictions and challenges. Children of the era of rapidly developing technology are also highly demanding and intelligent. Nowadays, it is becoming extremely difficult to surprise or astonish young people with any issue. The worldview of today's young audience is completely different. There are almost no children left who believe in fairy tales or are frightened by the wolf-bailiff or fox-messenger. If you tell them something, you must always be ready to give a serious and convincing answer to the question "Why?". Therefore, the education and upbringing provided to them remain among the most important issues. Most of our young people are becoming attached to the Internet, mobile phones, smartphones, and computers. In this regard, it is an urgent task to attract their attention to educational means that can protect them from the negative influences and attacks of the Internet. Today, there is a growing need to instill national ideology, national culture, and spirituality in the hearts of our youth, thereby forming immunity against the invasion of mass culture. In this matter, it is advisable to properly utilize the role, importance, and power of literature, art, and culture. Indeed, it is no secret that the boundaries of this power are limitless.

Regarding the role and significance of art and culture in society, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, stated the following during a meeting with cultural and artistic figures of Uzbekistan on April 1, 2026:

"The economy raises the state, laws govern it, and the army protects it. But the future of any country that pays attention to literature and culture will be strong. Any society that values creativity and art will have strong spiritual immunity.

One good work, one influential song raises the spirit of a nation; a single performance awakens the thinking of society; one character in a film can change the outlook of an entire generation." Theatre, in particular, serves as a mirror for people and is one of the most effective means of spiritual upliftment in society.

Theatre is a mirror of spirituality and a true center of education. Its essence lies in the important task of enriching a person's spiritual world and elevating culture. Such stage works should reflect the destiny of the nation, human life, and the joys and sorrows of the homeland. Mahmudhoja Behbudiy once said, "The theatre is a house of example." Indeed, the main purpose of theatre is to provide spiritual nourishment to the audience during a performance and encourage them to think and draw conclusions.

This mission also applies to puppet theatre and, in fact, forms its main criterion. Although the history of puppet theatre shows that its performances were originally intended for adults, today it is widely perceived as a theatre for children. In this respect, puppet theatre serves as a key link in

shaping and educating human spirituality. The renowned scholar, Honored Scientist of Uzbekistan, Doctor of Art Studies, and Professor Mukhsin Qodirov highly valued puppet theatre art and explained:

"Asian puppet theatre is not merely entertainment; it is an important historical and artistic phenomenon closely connected with the philosophy, visual arts, and languages of the peoples of an entire continent." A child who looks at the world with wonder possesses a mind like a blank sheet of paper and an equally pure heart. In this sense, education is a process that requires careful consideration, caution, and deep intellectual approach. According to psychologists, until the age of three a person strives to become acquainted with the surrounding world, and from the ages of three to seven seeks to understand it. Science has proven that throughout the rest of life, newly acquired information is either accepted or rejected through comparative analysis with knowledge gained during this period.

Although this principle has long been part of the traditions of the Uzbek people, unfortunately, it seems to be gradually fading over time. The childhoods of great ancestors such as Mir Alisher Navoi, Babur, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Imam Bukhari, Al-Farghani, At-Termizi, Az-Zamakhshari, and many others serve as evidence of this statement.

At first glance, the seemingly simple period from three to seven years of age places a significant responsibility on parents and those around the child regarding what kind of individual the child will become. We must remember that the issue concerns not only a single individual but also the society formed by such individuals and the force that determines the future and destiny of the country. Therefore, the upbringing of a harmoniously developed generation is a complex process that places enormous responsibility on all adults. The Uzbek people have been familiar with all forms of puppet performance art since ancient times. Over centuries, this art has reflected the worldview, aspirations, interests, and tastes of the masses. It has protected their interests and developed from generation to generation through new experiences and traditions. This blessed tradition continues today. In particular, on May 26, 2020, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev signed Decree No. PF-6000 "On Measures to Further Increase the Role and Influence of Culture and Art in the Life of Society." According to this decree, several issues that had long served as creative restrictions and obstacles for cultural and artistic figures found solutions. Taking into account its rich history and invaluable contribution to the formation and development of the Uzbek national puppet theatre school, the State Puppet Theatre was granted the status of the Uzbek National Puppet Theatre. This was recognized as a significant acknowledgment for the creative team working in this field and as a tribute to those who had created and contributed to this institution. The decree also envisaged the construction and modern technical equipment of four new state puppet theatres in the regions of Navoi, Namangan, Syrdarya, and Tashkent, which previously lacked puppet theatres. Furthermore, between 2021 and 2023, ten existing state puppet theatres were scheduled for capital renovation, reconstruction, and modernization in accordance with international professional standards. This demonstrates that specialists in the field truly felt the spirit of a professional celebration on that day. Indeed, the upbringing of youth has been elevated to the level of state policy in our country. The decree became another reliable step in this direction. As a result, the number of state puppet theatres in the republic reached fourteen. We know that among all forms of art, puppet theatre is one of the most ancient and is regarded as the cradle of all theatres. It is a unique art form with rich traditions and history. Its roots are closely connected with folklore, customs, traditions, and national values, which it has enriched and refined over centuries.

Its stage is filled with magical fairy tales, cheerful adventures, and events that correspond to children's psychology, occupy a bright place in their imagination, and lead them toward pure dreams. These performances consist of adventures and didactic works suited to children's interests and encompass a wide range of educational and thematic content. As People's Artist of Uzbekistan

and distinguished director Bahodir Yuldoshev emphasized: "The theatre does not educate the audience; only an educated audience comes to the theatre. People come to the theatre not merely to watch a performance but to empathize with the characters." Archaeological studies conducted in our country have revealed clay toys, unusual animal figures, whistles, and dolls in ancient fortresses and settlements. Such findings are unique evidence that many forms of art existed and developed in our land from ancient times. Puppet theatre is no exception. It is among the oldest forms of our artistic heritage. Puppet theatre gained popularity among the people because of its attractiveness, emotional impact, and simplicity. Traditionally known as "puppet play," its forms included glove puppets, string puppets, and shadow puppets. These were known as "Chodir Jamol" and "Chodir Hayol." Groups of puppeteers traveled through the dusty roads of Central Asia, regardless of heat or cold, sometimes by cart and sometimes on foot, moving from village to village and performing in caravanserais, crowded markets, and public squares.

Since Uzbekistan gained independence, puppet theatres operating in the country have continuously contributed to the ideological, spiritual, and aesthetic education of the younger generation. Specialists know that selecting a repertoire and determining methods of expressing themes and ideas are among the most complex processes in puppet theatre. Since audiences consist of children of different ages, plays cannot be written or selected without considering their age. Therefore, it is important to divide young audiences into three categories. The first category includes children aged 3–5. Plays for them should contain simple language, clear actions, and game-like structures. Puppet characters, props, and scenery should be colorful and attractive enough to captivate young viewers immediately. Cheerful games, songs, and musical effects should also be carefully selected. Themes should include scenes from children's lives, animals, nature, birds, and human relationships with nature and family. Such performances help children observe, analyze, and develop educational concepts, fostering understanding, kindness, and interaction with characters. Examples include M. Ashurova's *Alla and Your Good Virtues Are Your Adornment*, Orlov's *The Golden Chick*, N. Gernet's *The Gosling*, and E. Khushvaqtov's *Mother's Love*. The second category consists of schoolchildren aged 6–9. Their plays usually focus on family, school, study, work, friendship, and kindness through adventures, magic, and fantasy. Such performances cultivate loyalty, honesty, resourcefulness, determination, compassion, and friendship. Examples include M. Ashurova's *Value Your Own Home*, *Hello Earthlings*, *We Are With You!*, *The Enchanted Prince*, V. Pavlovsky's *Pea Boy*, Y. Toychiyev's *Fulfillment of a Dream*, and E. Speransky's *The Amazing Race*. These performances are primarily action-based, with words used purposefully and sparingly. In this respect, puppet theatre differs from dramatic theatre. As Professor S. Qodirova explains: "A play written for puppet theatre should not be distinguished merely by its small size, but by its action-based structure, clear purpose and idea, and avoidance of excessive verbosity. After all, a puppet finds it difficult to express long monologues and moralizing speeches." The third category includes children aged 9–12. Plays for them should address national traditions, customs, values, historical figures, and their contributions to world civilization. Positive heroes should be patriotic, determined, capable of overcoming obstacles, and striving for progressive ideals. Such works help children define life goals and inspire courage, loyalty, humanity, nobility, and compassion. Examples include Alisher Navoi's *Muqbil and Mudbir and The Language of Birds*, M. Ashurova's *The Cry of the Swans* and *Sindbad the Sailor*, Sh. Usmonova and B. Eshonqulov's *The Star of Ulughbek*, and Sh. Murodov's *The Scholar Who Flew in the Skies*. As Shomurod Yusupov, Chief Director of the Uzbek National Puppet Theatre and Honored Artist of Uzbekistan, noted:

"If young audiences grow up watching performances of true artistic value, they will certainly become educated theatre-goers in the future. In short, every artist must work selflessly to develop and advance puppet theatre art."

The theme, system of events, conflicts and their resolutions, characters, and their specific features are all interconnected. These criteria unfold differently under various circumstances and stages within a work. Therefore, if a director accurately assesses the audience's age and perception abilities and finds an appropriate directorial solution, the success of the performance is ensured. Thus, puppet theatre, and theatre art in general, possesses unique educational, ideological, and aesthetic functions in the upbringing of the younger generation. In Uzbekistan, all necessary measures are being taken to support this field. As an Indian thinker and statesman once said: "If we wish to establish peace in the world, we must begin with the education of children." Let us not forget: "Puppet theatre is the foundation of the future." The development of Uzbekistan's art and culture, as well as the future progress of the field, lies in the hands of young specialists who are receiving profound knowledge and thorough training today. These young people, in turn, receive their first lessons in upbringing from puppet theatres, which serve as a solid foundation for their future.

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